

Research Fund for Coal and Steel

Grant Agreement Number

101034041

Modelling of hydrogen activity from atmospheric corrosion in ultra-high strength steels for light structure application

AtHyCor

Deliverable D14:

Application guidelines to anticipate hydrogen assisted cracking under atmospheric corrosion conditions

Due date of deliverable: 30/06/2024

Actual submission date : 29/08/2024

Period covered by the Deliverable:

01/07/2022 – 30/06/2024

Start date of project: **01/07/2021**

Duration: **36 months**

Organization name of lead contractor for this deliverable:

Institut de la Corrosion

1. Introduction

As part of the AtHyCor project, comprehensive investigations were carried out to assess the local corrosion mechanisms that could lead to hydrogen production in press-hardened steels (PHS) with various protective coatings, including GI and AlSi. A set of advanced characterization tools was employed, such as Scanning Vibrating Electrode Technique (SVET), Scanning Kelvin Probe (SKP), electrochemical permeation test (EPT), thermal desorption spectrometry (TDS), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and the respirometric method. In parallel, mechanical tests were performed under different corrosive conditions to evaluate the potential risk of hydrogen embrittlement.

Based on these findings, models of atmospheric corrosion and hydrogen trapping were developed and integrated within the COMSOL framework. The atmospheric corrosion model covers all critical mechanisms, enabling predictions of corrosion product formation, surface pH distribution, hydrogen evolution reactions (HER), and oxygen reduction reactions (ORR). Additionally, the model simulates the lattice and trapped hydrogen distribution within the steel under varying hydrogen entry conditions, revealing local over-concentrations due to surface hydrogen activity or plastic deformation.

This report provides a thorough critical review of the experiments and results and discusses a methodology for assessing the risk of hydrogen cracking under real-world vehicle conditions.

2. Corrosion mechanisms

In the work packages 3 and 4 of the project, the corrosion behaviour of the coated PHS was assessed at meso and micro-scales.

The intensity of the galvanic coupling between the GI coating and the steel could be evaluated thanks to the SVET experiments. The impact of the coating composition could be quantified, and test conditions modified, in particular acidified, to be as close as possible to atmospheric corrosion conditions. The data are particularly valuable for the development of atmospheric corrosion models.

Combining the results from the different characterization methods, the corrosion mechanisms of the coated PHS materials could be further described, as it will be soon reported in the paper under revision at the writing of this report: N. Macháčková, T. Prošek, G. Luckeneder, “Corrosion mechanism of press-hardened steel with zinc coating in controlled atmospheric conditions: A laboratory investigation”. Another paper was also under preparation by the same main author related to the corrosion mechanism of PHS AlSi material.

The SKP method was also utilized to evaluate anodic and cathodic polarization curves under thin film conditions. These polarization curves provide critical data to investigate the atmospheric corrosion processes. The ability of This is also very valuable for the development and refinement of numerical models, significantly boosting their ability to predict corrosion behaviour and material degradation with greater precision. As a result, the integration of SKP-derived polarization data into modelling frameworks can lead to more robust and reliable predictions, particularly in complex environments where conventional bulk measurements may fall short. Such data have been shared with the scientific community through the paper: V. Helbert, A. Nazarov, M. Taryba, F. Vucko, F. Montemor, D. Thierry, Kinetics of electrochemical reactions on press hardened steel under simulated atmospheric corrosion conditions using local techniques, *Electrochimica Acta* Vol. 458 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2023.142500>.

3. Accelerated corrosion tests vs real outdoor conditions

The corrosion behaviour of coated steels was evaluated under various accelerated test conditions and after two winter periods on a trailer, submitted to real outdoor conditions representative of vehicles. Comparing the corrosion

attack observed in these two types of exposure provided valuable insights into the relevance and effectiveness of accelerated corrosion tests for predicting service-related corrosion. Notably, it was observed that the acceleration factor in these tests was extremely high, which could significantly influence the hydrogen sensitivity of the test specimens. Corrosion sensors also provided useful data regarding the acceleration factor during critical phases of corrosion, particularly during the winter period, although the observed acceleration was still few orders of magnitude lower than that achievable through accelerated corrosion tests.

Given that increasing the severity of corrosive conditions in testing environments typically leads to increased hydrogen activity, it is estimated that an optimal accelerated corrosion test should aim to replicate the extreme corrosion rates observed in real outdoor conditions. This would enable a more accurate anticipation of failure risks. Currently, most accelerated corrosion tests are designed to save time during material qualification, which is effective for assessing the risk of paint and coating degradation. However, these tests are not well-suited for predicting the risk of hydrogen embrittlement caused by atmospheric corrosion. Developing new tests specifically tailored to evaluate the risk of hydrogen embrittlement would be highly beneficial, particularly for qualifying very high-strength steels, where such risks are more pronounced.

4. HER and hydrogen uptake evaluation

Hydrogen production and activity at the surface of the steel was investigated in work packages 3 and 5.

A combination of respirometry measurements and EPT or SKP can be used to get direct information about HER and hydrogen activity at the surface of the steel. This is a critical information for the development of accurate hydrogen model, where the real activity of hydrogen representative of atmospheric corrosion is clear lacking in the literature. This gap was filled with a first paper: N. Macháčková, D. Rudomilova, T. Prošek, Respirometry, a new approach for investigation of the relationship between corrosion-induced hydrogen evolution and its entry into metallic materials, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 65, 817-828, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.04.045>. Another paper, from the same authors, with a combination of SKP and respirometry was still under preparation at the end of the project and will be shared with the scientific community as soon as possible.

EPT under atmospheric corrosion conditions can also be used to assess the hydrogen activity under atmospheric corrosion conditions. As a non-local technique, the interpretation of the data can greatly benefit from accurate diffusion model. The combination of SKP and EPT can be used to calibrate the SKP signal, which make the technique both local and quantitative. The method has been described in the paper: F Vucko, V Helbert, A Nazarov, Quantification of Hydrogen Flux from Atmospheric Corrosion of Steel Using the Scanning Kelvin Probe Technique, *Metals*, 2023 <https://doi.org/10.3390/met13081427>.

Thus, a combination of SKP, respirometry, electrochemistry and permeation, completed with thermal desorption analyses to evaluate the hydrogen content in the corroded specimens have to be used to correctly assess the hydrogen activity under atmospheric conditions, helping at interpreting mechanical tests under the same conditions and selecting the right boundary conditions of hydrogen distribution models.

5. Severity of the methods to evaluate hydrogen embrittlement for service conditions

In the automotive sector, various methods have been developed to assess the risk of service failure related to hydrogen embrittlement. Among these, Slow Strain Rate Testing (SSRT) and 4-point bending (4PB) were selected for the project. However, other methods, including tests with punched-hole specimens, shear-cut tensile specimens, U-bend specimens, or cup specimens, are commonly referenced in the standards and specifications of automotive manufacturers.

SSRT is particularly valuable due to its high response to hydrogen embrittlement, which arises from the non-static

load applied to the specimens. Under slow strain rate conditions, the interaction between the microstructure, in particular dislocations, and hydrogen is enhanced, maximizing its impact on ductility compared to conventional or fast tensile testing. The slower the strain rate, the greater the susceptibility of high-strength steels to hydrogen embrittlement. By employing SSRT under controlled corrosive conditions, with or without annealing treatments to remove hydrogen and isolate the effect of corrosion, critical insights were gained into the sensitivity of the tested steels. Notably, SSRT highlighted the significant role of defects in the zinc layer, whether pre-existing or introduced during plastic deformation, in increasing the susceptibility of specimens to failure under atmospheric corrosion conditions.

In contrast, 4PB testing, as a constant load type of testing, subjects the materials to less severe mechanical conditions. This method is particularly suited for PHS, which are designed to be used without further plastic deformation, as the forming process occurs at high temperatures. Under the conditions tested, which involved standard accelerated corrosion tests, it was observed that failure was primarily linked to the cutting process of the specimen edges. Shear cutting introduced local defects and residual stresses that are especially detrimental in the presence of hydrogen, particularly for steels sensitive to hydrogen embrittlement. This finding highlights the importance of selecting adapted cutting processes and proper component designs to significantly reduce the risk of failure of PHS components.

6. Discussion

Ultra-high-strength steels, such as PHS, with tensile strengths exceeding 1500 MPa, are known to be particularly susceptible to hydrogen embrittlement under severe hydrogen charging conditions. These conditions include exposure to acidic environments (such as pickling baths), cathodic hydrogen charging, or immersion in saltwater with zinc-based coatings. While these harsh conditions can be useful for ranking the relative susceptibility of different materials, they do not necessarily provide a clear indication of the performance of the steel in real-world service environments. The assumption that material rankings under extreme conditions will remain consistent under less severe, more realistic corrosion conditions is not always valid, as the mechanisms of hydrogen embrittlement may differ significantly.

In automotive applications, the primary concern for structural components is atmospheric corrosion, often influenced by factors such as salt deposits (e.g., de-icing salts, marine salts, road mud), and cycles of wet and dry phases linked to local climate and weather conditions. The automotive industry has developed accelerated corrosion tests primarily to assess the degradation of paints and coatings; however, there is no consensus on the optimal test conditions. This lack of consensus stems from the absence of a universal test capable of simulating all climate and local variations.

For hydrogen embrittlement testing specifically, the role of hydrogen activity, influenced by the severity of corrosion conditions, is critical. When comparing real-world outdoor conditions, such as those observed in samples exposed on a trailer in Sweden, to accelerated laboratory tests, it has been found that the corrosion rate in accelerated tests can be at least ten times higher than the maximum values recorded under service conditions. Experimental techniques like SKP and EPT, along with simulations of atmospheric corrosion in thin films, have demonstrated that more severe corrosion conditions, characterized by thinner water layers with higher salt concentrations, elevated temperatures, and intense salt contamination, lead to increased hydrogen evolution reaction and hydrogen uptake. Consequently, standard accelerated corrosion tests used to assess the risk of service failure due to hydrogen embrittlement tend to be quite conservative, if not entirely unrealistic.

Further research is required to better understand the relationship between environmental conditions, hydrogen uptake, and the risk of failure in a wider range of steel grades and service conditions. This will enable the development of more accurate testing methodologies. The tools and techniques developed and validated in this project should now be applied systematically and statistically to achieve this goal.